
**ITEM RESPONSE THEORY IN THE CONTEXT OF INFORMATION
AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY: A LITERATURE
REVIEW OF SCALE DEVELOPMENT AND APPLICATION**

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ABSTRACT

To capture the perceptions of users of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), Item Response Theory (IRT) stands out as a robust and effective statistical tool for evaluating latent variable scales. This article employs a systematic search methodology, utilizing Mendeley software, to investigate the application of IRT scales within the ICT context, with a particular focus on the quality evaluation of the scales used in each identified study, based on DeVellis' (2017) guide. The search was conducted using the EBSCO, SCOPUS, and Web of Science databases. The literature review identified sixteen articles that applied IRT to ICT-related scenarios. These studies employed a variety of IRT models, including the Gradual Response Model, One-, Two-, and Three-Parameter Logistic Models, the One-Dimensional Graduated Unfolding Model, and Multidimensional Models. Despite IRT's versatility and methodological strength, the review revealed a notable scarcity of its application in technological contexts. Furthermore, a significant gap was identified in the initial development of precise and coherent scales for ICT assessments, suggesting a need for more focused efforts in this area of research.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology; Item Response theory; measurement scales.

1 INTRODUCTION

The changes initiated through development processes reflect a society increasingly influenced by technological resources and the rapid advancement of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). These technologies significantly impact social and organizational relations, making ICTs vital drivers of change globally. As a dynamic force for innovation, they have become indispensable for countries and their populations [20].

The development of hardware and software facilitates communication and processes in virtual environments. The Internet's popularization has enhanced ICT usage across various sectors, creating new communication systems that revolutionize human relationships. In this context, statistics can integrate with ICTs to improve applications [26]. Statistical software has become essential for robust analytical applications, reinforcing ICTs as valuable tools in developing methodological frameworks [34].

Among statistical analyses, Item Response Theory (IRT) has gained prominence. This set of statistical models aims to evaluate individuals' responses to test items [15]. IRT is used to develop, evaluate, and apply standardized scales [4], estimating parameters like difficulty, discrimination, and casual hit rate [10]. Thus, IRT serves as an effective tool for analyzing user perceptions of ICTs, which are deeply embedded in contemporary society. However, developing an appropriate measurement scale and selecting suitable statistical instruments is crucial. Every research instrument must undergo reliability and validity assessments to ensure its applicability.

The exponential growth of ICT usage over the past decade is well-documented [33], [34]. The latent variables in this field are complex and closely linked to user perceptions [35]. Therefore, robust, multidimensional modeling is essential for creating effective measurement scales [34]. IRT models are well-validated and applicable across diverse fields such as education, psychology, and technology. Their use highlights the importance of statistical validity and confidence in the findings [23], [25], [27].

Given this context, a pertinent question arises: how has Item Response Theory been applied to Information and Communication Technology? While the use of IRT is well-established, research focused on ICTs utilizing this statistical tool remains limited. This study aims to explore IRT application in ICTs and evaluate the quality of the scales used in identified research. A systematic search methodology was employed across various literature databases, leading to an analysis of the articles and their approaches. Previous literature reviews in this area were not found, emphasizing the originality of this study.

This research highlights the most frequently used IRT models in ICT studies and focuses on latent variables related to user perception scales and the specific ICTs addressed in the literature. It also illustrates authors with the most published research in a network graph, alongside the annual publication count. Nevertheless, the study identified a notable lack of IRT

modeling in technological contexts, despite its broad applicability and robustness, as well as insufficient attention to foundational elements in scale creation.

2 IRT IN THE CONTEXT OF ICT

Item Response Theory (IRT) comprises a collection of statistical models designed to estimate latent traits through a set of items and the construction of scales. This approach allows for comparing the respondent's latent trait with the difficulty of specific items [17]. The appropriate IRT model is chosen based on item type and represents the probability of a response, influenced by the respondent's proficiency and item parameters [31]. The difficulty parameters and individual proficiency are estimated on a standardized latent trait scale, where a higher score indicates a greater degree of the measured trait, and a lower score indicates less [10].

IRT facilitates item analysis, computerized adaptive testing, and evaluation of differential item functioning [15]. It enables the development of measurement scales grounded in mathematical and behavioral concepts to enhance understanding of technological systems [2]. Compared to Classical Test Theory, IRT offers advantages in measuring latent traits, allowing comparisons between populations through common items and between individuals taking different tests [2]. This model uniquely treats each item independently, ensuring that conclusions are based on individual item responses rather than the test as a whole [28]. The probability of a correct response is directly proportional to the individual's ability, indicating that higher ability corresponds to a greater likelihood of success [2].

In defining the appropriate IRT model, three key factors must be considered: the nature of the items (dichotomous or polytomous), the number of populations involved, and the number of latent traits being measured [2]. IRT has applications across various fields, including health [6], education [3], and psychology [19]. This article specifically explores IRT's application within the context of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs), which have expanded significantly over the past decade [33], [34], [35].

ICTs encompass all technology tools used for managing information and enhancing communication, including hardware, software, and networking [14]. These technologies significantly influence social interactions, altering how relationships are formed and maintained across various contexts. The rise of the Information Age has made information and knowledge

crucial for individuals in modern society, often referred to as the Information and Knowledge Society [14]. In this landscape, IRT emerges as a robust tool for capturing and evaluating user perceptions effectively [2].

Moreover, ICTs connect individuals irrespective of distance, proving invaluable for communication and marketing. Understanding users' perceptions of these technologies is essential, especially as society becomes increasingly reliant on them. IRT serves as a powerful instrument for analyzing user perceptions and provides a comprehensive understanding of how individuals interact with technology. Thus, applying IRT to explore ICTs is both beneficial and practical, despite its underutilization [15], [17].

3 METHODOLOGY

To meet the objective of the study, we chose to elaborate a systematic search of the literature, because it allows the realization of a planned selection of papers, through explicit and replicable methods of search, selection, and analysis [22]. The systematic search aims to identify, evaluate, and summarize the results of relevant studies, making the data more accessible to decision-makers. Among the several types of literature reviews, the Theoretical review has some similarities with this study, especially concerning comprehensive strategy and broad scope [26].

Related to the application theme of IRT around ICTs, no previous systematic reviews were found. To synthesize the literature on the subject and contribute to a future research agenda, aspects recommended by the PRISMA model [24] were adopted, especially the eligibility, analysis, and communication criteria of the research applicable to systematic reviews. For this systematic review, eligibility criteria, information sources, study selection, data collection process, risk of bias in studies, summary measures, synthesis of results, risk of bias between studies, and additional analyses.

The inclusion criteria of the studies were defined as follows:

- a) Articles indexed in the databases: SCOPUS, EBSCO, and Web of Science.
- b) Full articles published in Portuguese or English.
- c) Articles published in journals or papers presented in scientific events, without a clipping period, exploring all articles from the databases.

d) Articles that apply the Item Response Theory in the context of Information and Communication Technology.

The searches were performed considering the search terms in the title, abstract, and keywords. The next step, after defining the inclusion criteria of the studies, was the definition of the search strategy, considering the most correct terms to be used to form the search query. Based on the author's study preferences, the following terms were defined as a search strategy: ("item response theory") AND ("information and communication technology" OR "*-commerce" OR "m-banking").

Figure 1 shows the selection process flow, done in January 2022, according to the PRISMA model and using the Mendeley software. For the selection of studies, 30 resulting articles were read and, after filtering the search for adherence to the theme, only 16 articles applied the statistical tool in the context of ICTs. We excluded 14 articles that dealt with some type of trade, but it was not e-commerce, besides removing articles that dealt only with the application of the in a general context, not technological.

Figure 1 - Selection Process Flow

Source: Prepared by the author.

The references were exported for analysis in the Microsoft Excel software, in which the following data were gathered: authors, year, title, journal, keywords, central theme, type of article, research strategy, main references, and country of university affiliation. To summarize and synthesize the results, the production of papers per journal over the years, the number of researchers, the number of countries in which they maintain university affiliation, the number of times prominent authors were cited, and the count of keywords were quantified. Together, the sixteen selected papers can discuss the application of the Item Response Theory in the conjuncture of technologies related to information and communication systems.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In consolidated terms, the sixteen articles under analysis also represent sixteen different scientific journals (or congresses) and a group of thirty-five researchers, affiliated with universities in nine countries. The articles are within a seventeen-year interval, from 2004 to 2021, according to Figure 2. This interval is short, although the IRT has been applied in the organizational world for a long time.

The varied number of universities, countries, and journals involved indicates that the Information and Communication Technology sector, and the way to approach it, through IRT, are diversified. Table 1 specifically highlights each ICT addressed in the selected articles, in addition to the dimensions analyzed through the IT in each article.

Figure 2 – The article's time interval

Source: Prepared by the author.

The selected articles have different themes of analysis, but the application of the IRT interconnects all. When analyzing the keywords of the articles, a total of 93 different keywords were totaled. Item Response Theory is recurring in all articles, and in addition, the keywords that appear were e-commerce and information technology. In the keyword cloud contained in Figure 3, these and other keywords found in the sixteen articles stand out visually.

Figure 3 - Keywords of articles

Source: Prepared by the author.

Table 1 highlights the selected articles, which addressed eleven different ICTs, with e-commerce excelling. Among the thirteen latent variables evidenced, there is variability, with recurrences of quality and usability in different articles. Fifteen papers were published in English, and one was published in Portuguese. Regarding the countries of origin, the university in which the authors maintain a bond was observed in the articles. The countries that appear are Germany, Brazil, the USA, India, Greece, Italy, Japan, Taiwan, and the city-state of Hong Kong.

Table 1 - Selected Articles

Authors	ICT	Dimension Analyzed
Achtenhagen and Winther (2014)	IT Organizations	Competence
Chen et al. (2004)	e-learning	Student capacity
Christoforaki and Ipeirotis (2015)	Skill test generation and evaluation system	Quality
De Souza and Tezza (2021)	m-banking	Perceived risk
Huggins et al. (2014)	ICT literacy tool	IT Literacy
Chung and Li (2006)	Custom travel material	Skill
Li et al. (2020)	e-sourcing	Experience
Melas et al. (2014)	Health information technology system	Attitude toward the use of evidence-based practice
Mitsutake et al. (2020)	e-health	Degree of education
Moreira Junior et al. (2013)	e-commerce	Usability
Peng et al. (2019)	e-commerce	Satisfaction
Primi et al. (2021)	Facebook	Addiction
Tezza et al. (2011)	e-commerce	Usability
Tezza et al. (2018)	e-commerce	Quality
Tezza et al. (2016)	e-commerce	Quality
Trierweiller et al. (2012)	IT Organizations	Effectiveness

Source: Prepared by the author.

The analysis of studies on Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) reveals a diverse range of contexts and dimensions explored by researchers. For example, Achtenhagen and Winther (2014) examined competence in IT organizations, while Chen et al. (2004) focused on student capacity in e-learning. Christoforaki and Ipeirotis (2015) assessed the quality of skill test generation systems, and De Souza and Tezza (2021) investigated perceived risk in m-banking. Additionally, e-commerce studies addressed usability and quality, with contributions from Moreira Junior et al. (2013) and Tezza et al. (2016). Overall, these studies highlight the multifaceted nature of ICT applications and the need to understand various user experiences and perceptions across different dimensions.

5 SCALES' EVALUATION

The systematic search showed sixteen articles that apply IRT in certain contexts of ICTs. And, regardless of the analysis conjuncture, the use of the statistical approach proved to be essential for the results achieved in each research. When working with quantitative research, the creation of a valid and reliable data collection instrument is essential. Therefore, the creation of a scale should follow steps that help in the development of a coherent and precise instrument.

To individually assess the scale proposed by each article, Table 2 presents a comparative analysis of the elaboration of each measurement scale. The guide presented by DeVellis [13] is used as a basis, whose steps include: (1) Clarity in the definition of the measure; (2) Generation of the item; (3) Choosing the proper measurement format; (4) Review of items by other experts; (4) Evaluation of the inclusion of validation items; (5) Pre-test application; (6) Assessment of individual item performance and (7) Scale optimization.

According to the comparative table, no article fulfilled all the steps suggested by DeVellis [13]. However, two works [11], and [20] pointed out all the steps. The sixteen articles most explored the initial procedures of clarity, generation of items, and choice of format. These steps are essential, since, based on the theoretical foundation of the studies, they aim to generate validity for the content that is conceived.

The first step in the development of a scale is clarity which refers to intelligibly exposing the construct to be measured [13], which is crucial for all types of work. The second refers to the generation of items, which was followed by most of the articles found, only two studies did not show this step [7], [9]. Regarding the third step, the definition of the format, along with the first step, was presented as the only steps of the guide fulfilled by all articles.

Table 2 - Scale evaluation elements

Authors	Clarity	Item generation	Format	Revision	Inclusion of items	Pre-test	Evaluation	Optimization
Achtenhagen and Winther (2014)	X	X	X	X	X			
Chen et al. (2004)	X		X					
Christoforaki and Ipeirotis (2015)	X	X	X	X	X	X		
Chung and Li (2006)	X		X					
De Souza and Tezza (2020)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Huggins et al. (2014)	X	X	X	X		X	X	
Li et al. (2020)	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	X
Melas et al. (2014)	X	X	X				X	
Mitsutake et al. (2020)	X	X	X				X	
Moreira Junior et al. (2013)	X	X	X	X				
Peng et al. (2019)	X	X	X				X	
Primi et al. (2021)	X	X	X				X	
Tezza et al. (2011)	X	X	X			X	X	
Tezza et al. (2018)	X	X	X	X			X	
Tezza et al. (2016)	X	X	X	X			X	
Trierweiler et al. (2012)	X	X	X	X		X		

Source: Prepared by the author, based on DeVellis (2017).

A solid and in-depth theoretical foundation is basic and essential. The articles evidenced here demonstrated this concern and presented reasoned themes. Before the application of the scale in the research sample, the opinion of specialists in the area was indispensable for some articles, since this emphasizes substantial validation [1], [8], [11], [18], [20], [21], [25], [33], [34], [35]. It is noteworthy that the other articles did not mention it. To add validity to the content, this stage is particularly important for the research, since it is strongly linked to the definition of the construct being examined [10], [13]. After this assessment, only a few articles highlighted the inclusion of new items in the scale [1], [8], [11], [20]. It is noteworthy that some

articles applied a ready-made scale, that is, the inclusion of items would not be part of the study [18], [21], [23], [25], [27], [28].

Another major step, and what happens after the opinion of the experts, is the development of a pre-test in the instrument created [13]. This step consists of its application to a small sample so that participants can give a personal and lay opinion on the subject dealt with. Only some articles evidenced the realization of this research stage [8], [11], [18], [20], [32], [35]. However, the other ten articles did not mention anything about this stage. The pre-test confirms whether there is a clear understanding of the issues. To generate a coherent scale, this stage generates validity for the content and the presentation to the experts. The researcher needs an isonomy of the items within the scale, and the performance of pre-tests helps in the generation of items that express exactly what is expected.

The seventh step is the assessment of the items and constitutes the core of the development of a scale. This procedure is initially performed by checking the correlation, score, and variance; followed by factor analysis and Cronbach's alpha evaluation [13]. Some articles did not mention it because they used a consolidated scale in their work [18], [21], [23], [25], [27], [28].

In the search for construct validity, the performance of a Factor analysis can contribute to the confirmation of the dimensions derived from the theoretical foundation. This analysis helps in the evaluation of the individual performance of the items so that only the appropriate ones remain and constitute the scale [16]. Despite its relevance, only some studies highlighted the application of factor analysis, exploratory or confirmatory, in their research instruments [11], [20], [21], [23], [27], [32], [33], [34]. Some authors who should do this step did not show it [1], [7], [8], [9], [18], [28], [35]. Exploratory factor analysis seeks to explore and define sets of highly correlated variables; confirmatory analysis seeks confirmation of constructs previously consolidated in the literature [16]. And the absence of this stage weakens the scale, lacking precision.

For the development of a reliable scale, internal consistency is a particularly crucial step. Represented by Cronbach's alpha, the evaluation of the reliability of the internal consistency of the measuring instruments indicates the homogeneity of the items within the scale dimensions [10]. Some articles also highlighted the appropriate values for this index (>0.6) [11], [18], [20],

[21], [23], [28], [32], [33]. However, five studies that were supposed to do this, didn't mention it [1], [7], [8], [9], [27], [34], [35].

It is noteworthy that six articles highlighted these two evaluation steps – factor analysis and Cronbach's alpha – in their work [11], [20], [21], [23], [32], [33].

Finally, the last step, optimization, consists of evaluating the choice between brevity and reliability to exclude bad items, given the desired size of the scale. The interpretation of an item as “good” or “bad” depends on its correlation with the other items and how much its deletion or maintenance can increase or decrease alpha. That is if when excluding an item, the alpha increases, it means that this is a bad item and should be excluded in the scale optimization step [13]. It is suggested to split the sample, using a subsample in the development and/or in the replication [13, p. 111]. In the selected systematic review sample, only two articles mentioned that step [11], [20].

Therefore, in general, the initial creation of the instrument items was carried out according to the way recommended by the literature [10], [13], following assumptions in clarity and choice of the appropriate format. While the following steps, which include content validations, item inclusions, specific evaluations, and optimization, were not evidenced by all authors. These steps are crucial for the elaboration of a valid and reliable scale. It is worth noting that the reliability of a scale shows the extent to which a scale produces consistent results if measurements are taken repeatedly; validity concerns its ability to measure what it intends [13].

The sixteen studies showed important steps highlighting validity and confidence in the scales. However, most studies did not highlight steps that ensured the accuracy and coherence of their respective data collection instruments. It is a clear need for emphasis on the initial stages of creating scales, which guarantee trust and validity. Reliability shows the extent to which a range produces consistent results if measurements are taken repeatedly; the validity of a scale concerns its ability to measure what it wants [10].

6 CONCLUSIONS

The primary objective of this study was to explore the application of Item Response Theory (IRT) scales within the context of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs). Through a systematic search, sixteen articles were identified, elucidating the most

frequently utilized IRT models, the authors with the highest co-participation, and the dimensions being investigated about ICTs. Thirteen latent variables emerged as significant research factors in IT studies, with the Two-Parameter Logistic Model and the Gradual Response Model being the most commonly applied IRT models.

The data used in these studies were predominantly dichotomous and polytomous, reflecting a balanced approach. An evaluation of the validity and reliability of the scales employed in each study was conducted, revealing that researchers generally sought internal consistency and content and construct validity to ensure unbiased results. Most studies included the presentation of research instruments to specialists and conducted pre-tests, thereby enhancing the quality of the developed scales. For a scale to be effective, it must be precise and applicable, and its reliability and validity must be thoroughly assessed to support the pertinence of the conclusions drawn.

The systematic search indicated a notable lack of emphasis on the foundational steps required for developing a measurement instrument, which is essential for creating accurate and coherent scales. The analysis of the scales developed in the sixteen articles highlighted the need for greater rigor in the initial stages of scale development. Although some studies considered essential steps, such as obtaining expert opinions and ensuring internal consistency, many articles focused only on a limited number of these critical processes.

In the theoretical context, this article contributes by underscoring crucial steps for developing scales that analyze ICTs. Its managerial implications are evident in identifying elements that pertain to the perceptual profiles of ICT users, which are vital for formulating strategies for the effective application of these platforms. In the academic sphere, this research addresses a relatively underexplored topic that has gained prominence during the pandemic. Future research should aim to explore scales related to other influential areas of technology, such as Artificial Intelligence, which encompasses machine learning, learning analytics, intelligent tutoring systems, artificial neural networks, and smart systems, among others.

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